

RoguePlots_CML-24-Morph: This pdf contains the RoguePlots created for the 24 fossils resulted from the analysis maximum likelihood analysis for 24 fossils using only morphological data (*CML-24-Morph*).

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X_Archaeanthus_linnenbergeri

BS

X_Bertilanthus_scanicus

BS

X_Carpestella_lacunata

BS

BS

X_Divisestylus_brevistamineus

BS

BS

BS

BS

BS

BS

BS

X_Rariglanda_jerseyensis

BS

BS

